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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to enhance the understanding of competitive adsorption and ion exchange of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and other industrial persistent, mobile and toxic substances (iPMT) in the presence of dissolved organic matter (DOM) and to optimize their removal from ground- and drinking water in fixed-bed filters. To achieve this, laboratory and pilot-scale experiments were combined with monitoring of a large-scale groundwater treatment plant with activated carbon at a legacy contaminated site.

In order to identify an optimal treatment train for PFAS removal, different high performance and tailored adsorbents were tested at laboratory scale and benchmarked against state-of-the-art granular activated carbon (GAC). Initially, a comprehensive adsorbent screening was conducted that involved a series of equilibrium jar tests using 18 different adsorbents and spiked drinking water (including 13 PFAS and 7 iPMT). These adsorbents were selected based on a literature research for high performance adsorbents for PFAS and iPMT removal and included several activated carbons, strong basic anion exchange resins as well as novel adsorbents such as surface modified clays, a cyclodextrin polymer, and a zeolite.

The results of the jar tests revealed that strong-base anion exchange resins (IX) were the most effective at removing PFAS. However, these IX were particularly vulnerable to competition from non-targeted DOM components. Activated carbons were found to be the most effective adsorbents in removing a wide range of iPMT, but they were ineffective at removing short-chain PFAS (which are by definition of the OECD all PFAS with less than 6 perfluorinated carbon atoms (ECD, 2021)). For the alternative adsorbents tested, there were significant variations in their ability to remove PFAS and iPMT, with the bentonite-based surface modified clays (SMC) showing considerable potential due to their high PFAS selectivity. In line with current literature, the results showed that PFAS removal increased with the length of the perfluorinated carbon chain. For compounds of the same chain length, those with a sulfonate group were removed more effectively than those with a carboxylate group.

Based on the results from the jar tests, three GAC products, two SMC, and two IX were selected for testing in laboratory rapid small-scale column tests (RSSCT) with spiked drinking water, including 15 PFAS and 8 iPMT. The RSSCT dataset was used to determine the breakthrough curves of all investigated compounds and to shortlist the adsorbents for subsequent piloting. In addition, the data was analyzed to identify possible synergies between adsorbents to identify the most promising treatment train. Usage rates were quantified for all adsorbents based on the RSSCT data.

In the subsequent piloting, an IX and a SMC, which had excelled in the laboratory tests, were piloted alongside a large-scale activated carbon plant. In addition, the most promising treatment train was tested, consisting of a combination of activated carbon and ion exchange. All process variants were tested at the same site for their ability to remove PFAS from legacy contaminated groundwater.

The target analysis in the pilot tests was supplemented by additional sampling campaigns for bioassay testing using TTR-TR β CALUX (PFAS CALUX) tests and for suspect screening. These results allow a more holistic evaluation of the adsorptive processes. All adsorbents tested were able to reduce the PFOA-equivalents in the PFAS CALUX tests. In the suspect screening, a lower number of substances was found in the GAC effluent than in the effluents of the SMC adsorber and the IX. This may indicate less selective removal by the activated carbon filter or leaching from the other adsorbents, but further studies may be of interest.

In the subsequent cost analysis, it became clear that the choice of a suitable adsorptive process is highly site-dependent in regards to the composition of the PFAS and iPMT, DOC concentration, and targeted effluent values. UV_{254} was found to be a potential surrogate parameter for real-time monitoring of PFAS removal by AC and IX.

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List of Abbreviations

AA	Alternative adsorbent
AAMPS	Sodium acryloyldimethyltaurate
AC	Activated carbon
ACE	Acesulfame
ADONA	Amino 2,2,3-trifluoro-3-[1,1,2,2,3,3-hexafluoro-3-(trifluoromethoxy)propoxy]propionate
ATA	Amantadine
BAFG	Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde
BB	Building blocks
BDMA	Benzyldimethylamine
BDS	BioDetection Systems
BEA	Beta zeolite
BETMAC	Benzyltrimethylazanium
BEQ	Biological PFOA equivalents
BP	Biopolymer
BTA	Benzotriazole
BWB	Berliner Wasserbetriebe
CBM	Carbamazepine
CDP	Cyclodextrin polymer
CEQ	Chemical PFOA equivalents
CG	Cyanoguanidine
DCF	Diclofenac
DIOTOG	Ditolylguanidine
DMBSA	2,4-dimethylbenzene-1-sulfonic acid
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
DOM	Dissolved organic matter
DTA	Diatrizoate
DW	Drinking water
EBCT	Empty bed contact time
GAC	Granular activated carbon
GW	Groundwater
H4-PFOS	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-tridecafluorooctane-1-sulfonic acid
HA	Humic acids
HFPO-DA	Perfluoro-2-propoxypropanoic acid
HPLC-MS/MS	High-performance liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry
HRMS	High-resolution mass spectrometry
IX	Ion exchange resin
LC-OCD	Liquid size-exclusion chromatography with UV ₂₅₄ and online organic carbon detection
LMWA	Low molecular weight acids
LMWN	Low molecular weight neutrals
LOQ	Level of quantification
MEL	Melamine
MPSA	Sodium 2-methylprop-2-ene-1-sulfonate
OMP	Organic micropollutant

PFBA	Perfluorobutyric acid
PFBS	Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid
PFHxS	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid
PFHpS	Perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid
PRI	Primidone
RSSCT	Rapid small-scale column tests
SAC	Saccharine
SF	Sand filter
SF	Scaling factor
SMC	Surface modified clay
SMX	Sulfamethoxazole
SOG	Activated carbon surface oxygen groups
TEQ	Trigger PFOA equivalents
TFMSA	Trifluoromethanesulfonic acid
TR	Thyroid hormone receptor
TTR	Transthyretin; transport protein for thyroxine (T4)
TTR-TR CALUX	Bioassay (PFAS CALUX)
UBA	Umweltbundesamt (German Environment Agency)
VSA	Valsartan acid

1 Introduction

The aim of this report is to enhance the understanding of competitive adsorption and ion exchange of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), industrial persistent mobile and toxic chemicals (iPMT) and other organic micropollutants (OMP) in the presence of dissolved organic matter (DOM) and to optimize their removal in fixed-bed filters. Laboratory and pilot-scale experiments were combined with monitoring of a large-scale groundwater (GW) treatment plant with granular activated carbon (GAC) at a legacy contaminated site. This work complements the Planning & Design Tool for Drinking Water Treatment for PFAS & Industrial Chemicals (D4.2) which was developed in PROMISCES and can be used to model different treatment trains for the adsorptive removal of PFAS and iPMT (Rückbeil et al., 2024).

The majority of full-scale treatments for PFAS and iPMT removal uses fixed-bed filters with GAC, with some plants targeting mainly PFAS also using ion exchange resins (IX) or high-pressure membrane filtration (Evich et al. 2022; Riegel et al. 2020; Boyer et al. 2021). Economical operation of fixed-bed filters with IX and GAC is usually hampered by early breakthroughs of short-chain PFAS and other iPMT, as well as competitive adsorption of DOM and inorganic anions (Dixit et al. 2020; Dixit et al. 2019; Gagliano et al. 2020; Riegel et al. 2023; Dixit et al. 2021a, Schumann et al., 2023).

Recently, a number of IX advertised as PFAS-specific have entered the market. In addition to ion exchange, the modified IX also rely on hydrophobic interactions between the hydrophobic perfluorinated carbon chain of the PFAS and the alkyl chains of the amino groups of the IX (Dixit et al. 2021b). Alternative adsorbents (AA), including functionalized carbonaceous materials, minerals, and polymers (Liu et al. 2024; Grieco et al. 2021), are increasingly being investigated for PFAS removal. Recent studies reported on the PFAS removal effectiveness of surface-modified clays (SMC) (Jiang et al. 2023; Plumlee et al. 2022; Pannu et al. 2023; Das et al. 2013), cyclodextrin polymers (CDP) (Ching et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2020) and beta polymorph A-type zeolites (BEA) (Qian et al. 2022; van den Bergh et al. 2020).

This report provides an overview of the performance of adsorbents which claim to be optimized for PFAS removal compared to the benchmark activated carbon (AC) technology. Furthermore, this study also investigated whether iPMT and other OMP can be removed in addition to PFAS.

For this purpose, Berlin tap water was used in the laboratory studies, which was spiked with highly concentrated stock solutions to an OMP concentration in the low $\mu\text{g/L}$ range. The test water thus contained significantly higher PFAS and iPMT concentrations than those expected in drinking water (DW) (Ingold et al., 2023 ; Neuwald et al. 2021; Schulze et al., 2019), but allowed a more robust quantification of the removal from water with high dissolved organic carbon (DOC) content (approx. 4-5 mg/L).

Initially, an adsorbent screening was conducted that involved a series of equilibrium jar tests using 18 different adsorbents tested for removal of 13 PFAS and 7 iPMTs. These adsorbents were selected based on a literature research for high performance adsorbents for PFAS and iPMT removal and included several AC, strong basic IX, as well as novel adsorbents such as SMC, cyclodextrin polymer, and zeolite.

Based on the results from the adsorbent screening (jar tests), three GAC products, two SMC, and two strong-basic anion IX were selected for testing in laboratory scale rapid small-scale column tests (RSSCT), including 15 PFAS and 8 iPMT. The RSSCT dataset was used to determine the breakthrough curves of all investigated compounds and to shortlist the adsorbents for subsequent piloting.

Usage rates (UR) are an established parameter to assess the efficiency of fixed-bed filter processes (Kempisty et al. 2022). Based on the RSSCT data, UR were quantified for 7 adsorbents and 32 OMP that were found in DW or DW resources (Neuwald et al. 2021; Schulze et al. 2019; Ingold et al. 2022).

In the subsequent piloting, an IX and a SMC, which excelled in the laboratory tests, were piloted alongside a large-scale GAC groundwater treatment plant for PFAS removal at a legacy contaminated site. In addition, the most promising treatment train was tested at pilot-scale, consisting of a combination of GAC and IX.

While over 100,000 substances are listed in the European chemical inventory, only a small fraction are monitored for environmental pollution. Non-target and suspect screening using high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) offers a comprehensive approach to detect and identify unforeseen contaminants, enabling retrospective studies of pollutant trends over time (Köppe et al., 2020; Dietrich et al., 2022). The new workflow for suspect screening of PFAS and iPMT was developed and detailed in PROMISCES D1.4 and applied in this case study (Dietrich et al., 2025). The PFAS CALUX assesses the thyroid-disrupting potential of bioaccumulating PFAS. It therefore has the potential to provide an impact-related assessment of water quality that can also consider PFAS that are not covered by target analysis (Behnisch et al., 2021a). A set of novel QSAR models and in vitro bioassay approaches predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals was developed in PROMISCES D1.5 and applied in this case study (Behnisch et al., 2021b). To gain a more holistic evaluation of the adsorbents, the target analysis in the pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant was therefore supplemented by additional sampling campaigns TTR-TR β CALUX (PFAS CALUX) bioassays and suspect screening.

Finally, the results of the pilot- and large-scale plant were evaluated by means of a summarized cost analysis and evaluation of UV₂₅₄ as real-time monitoring parameter to complete the comprehensive assessment.

2 Methodology

2.1 Investigated PFAS, iPMT and other OMP

Among all 33 OMP examined in the laboratory studies, 15 PFAS with different perfluorinated carbon (C) chain lengths and functional groups were included. According to the widely accepted PFAS definition by the OECD (2021), all PFAS with six or more perfluorinated C atoms are classified as long-chain PFAS.

The tested PFAS comprised seven perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCA), namely perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), perfluoropentanoic acids (PFPeA), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), and perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), as well as two perfluoroalkyl ether carboxylic acids (PFECA), perfluoro-2-propoxypropanoic acid (HFPO-DA) and Amino 2,2,3-trifluoro-3-[1,1,2,2,3,3-hexafluoro-3-(trifluoromethoxy)propoxy]-propionate (ADONA).

Furthermore, five perfluorosulfonic acids (PFSA) were tested: trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (TFMSA), perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS), perfluoropentanesulfonic acid (PFPeS), perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS), and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), as well as the PFOS substitute 3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-tridecafluorooctane-1-sulfonic acid (H4-PFOS).

In addition to PFAS, 18 other OMP were investigated that were detected in DW or DW resources (Neuwald et al. 2021; Schulze et al. 2019). This includes the nine iPMT sodium acryloyldimethyltaurate (AAMPS), benzyldimethylamine (BDMA), benzyltrimethylazanium (BETMAC), benzotriazole (BTA), cyanoguanidine (CG), ditolylguanidine (DIOTOG), 2,4-dimethylbenzene-1-sulfonic acid (DMBSA), melamine (MEL) and sodium 2-methylprop-2-ene-1-sulfonate (MPSA), as well as the five pharmaceuticals amantadine (ATA), carbamazepine (CBM), diclofenac (DCF), primidone (PRI), and sulfamethoxazole (SMX).

Furthermore, one X-ray contrast agent (diatrizoic acid (DTA)), the transformation product valsartan acid (VSA), and two sweeteners (acesulfame (ACE) and saccharin (SAC)) were included.

The pilot- and large-scale study was performed with PFAS-contaminated groundwater which contained quantifiable amounts (> level of quantification (LOQ)) of 5 PFCA, namely PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA and PFOA as well as 5 PFSA, namely PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid (PFHpS) and PFOS.

2.2 Adsorbent selection

In total, 18 adsorbents including six AC, five IX, five SMC, one CDP, and one BEA were investigated in initial screening using jar tests.

While AC1 to AC4 of four different manufacturers are agglomerated bituminous coals, AC5 is an extruded charcoal and AC6 an agglomerated lignite coal. The five strong-base IX with polystyrene polymer matrix advertised as PFAS-specific were delivered with Cl⁻ loading. IX1 is the only macroporous resin, whereas the other products (IX2 to IX5) are gellular.

SMC1 and SMC2 from the same manufacturer are functionalized with aliphatic amines resulting in quaternary ammonia groups. Whereas SMC1 is a commercialized product, SMC2 is a new product under development. The original natural clay material bentonite of SMC1 and SMC2 is mainly composed of montmorillonite, a 2:1 aluminosilicate (one octahedral sheet between two tetrahedral sheets). SMC3 to SMC5 were purchased from the same manufacturer, with SMC3 and SMC5 being based on palygorskite, a fibrous aluminosilicate. SMC3 and SMC5 were functionalized with fatty amines, namely oleylamine and octyl amine, resulting in quaternary ammonia groups. SMC4 is a mixture of SMC3 and AC.

The BEA was characterized in detail by Qian et al. (2022). The CDP is a β -cyclodextrin polymer functionalized with aliphatic amines, also resulting in quaternary ammonia groups. All adsorbents which could not be assigned to either AC or IX - namely SMC, CDP, and BEA - were categorized as AA.

The seven most promising adsorbents in the jar test screening (IX1, IX2, SMC1, SMC2, AC1, AC2, AC3) were investigated in more detail in RSSCT experiments. The results of the RSSCT screening were in turn used to select two adsorbents for subsequent piloting (IX1 and SMC1). The large-scale GAC plant operates with granular bituminous carbon GAC1. At the beginning of the large-scale operation, the first GAC adsorbents in series (A1 and B1) were operated with a coconut-based carbon (GAC7), which was not included in the lab-scale adsorbent screening.

2.3 Laboratory scale adsorbent testing

2.3.1 Jar tests

Drinking water from Berlin (4.5 mg/L DOC, pH of 7.5, more parameters in Table SI 1) was spiked with an OMP stock solution containing 12 PFAS and 7 iPMT. The resulting concentrations in the test water

are shown in Table SI 2. All adsorbents (except BEA, CDP, and SMC5, which were already supplied in powder form) were pulverized in a cryogenic ball mill (Retsch, Germany) to obtain faster and more uniform kinetics. Batches of 100 mL with 20 and 50 mg/L adsorbent (dry weight) were agitated for 48 h on a horizontal shaker in 175 mL polypropylene tubes (Falcon, Germany). A reference sample (c_0) without adsorbent was prepared the same way and also agitated for 48 h. After 48 h, samples were filtered using 0.45 μm membrane filters (regenerated cellulose, Macherey-Nagel, Germany, pre-rinsed with 10 mL ultra-pure water). Samples for PFAS analysis were stored at 4°C in polypropylene tubes (Th. Geyer, Germany), all other OMP samples were stored in glass vials (Roth, Germany). In order to compare with results of different studies, single point adsorption coefficients K_d were calculated by equation (1) using the equilibrium concentrations c_e and adsorbent loadings q_e as described by Worch et al. (2012):

$$K_d = \frac{q_e}{c_e} \quad (1)$$

2.3.2 RSSCT

With the help of RSSCTs, the breakthrough behavior of substances in a large-scale adsorber column can be approximated at laboratory scale (Worch 2012). By using a scaling method, RSSCTs require only a fraction of time, water, and material quantities that a large pilot column would need to achieve breakthrough. As a result, the method enables a rapid and cost-effective assessment of adsorbents with regard to their ability to remove certain target substances (Worch 2012; Schaefer et al. 2020).

The scaling approach based on mass transfer models guarantees that the flow conditions in the small column correspond to those in the large-scale column, and that the contribution of the individual mass transfer processes remains similar. The calculation of the dimensions of the RSSCT is based on a scaling factor (SF). This scaling factor for the empty bed contact time (EBCT) and the run time (t) results from the ratio of the particle diameters (d_p) of the adsorbents used in the laboratory column (SC) and in the large-scale filter (LC). The parameter x determines the dependence of the intraparticle diffusion properties on the particle diameter. The SF is calculated with equation (2) according to Worch et al. (2012) as follows:

$$SF = \frac{EBCT_{SC}}{EBCT_{LC}} = \left(\frac{d_{p,SC}}{d_{p,LC}} \right)^{2-x} = \frac{t_{SC}}{t_{LC}} \quad (2)$$

There are two main scaling approaches for RSSCTs (Crittenden et al. 1986; Crittenden et al. 1987). The constant diffusivity (CD) model assumes that the diffusion coefficients are independent of the particle diameter ($x = 0$). In the proportional diffusivity (PD) model, it is assumed that the coefficients change proportionally to the particle size ($x = 1$).

In order to achieve the desired particle size reduction, each adsorbent was ground using an electric mortar grinder (Pulverisette, Retsch, Germany) and then transferred to deionized water to swell overnight and was then degassed under vacuum. The adsorbents were wet sieved over stainless steel sieves (Retsch, Germany) with diameters of 140 μm and 90 μm to achieve a mean particle size of 115 μm . The flow rates of the RSSCT were set as low as possible to minimize the amount of test water needed but were also high enough to ensure that the dimensionless Reynolds number (Re) and the product of Re and the dimensionless Schmidt number (Sc) were ≥ 500 (Crittenden et al. 1986; Worch 2012; Kearns et al. 2020). The final design parameters of the RSSCT, after application of the CD scaling approach, are shown in Table 1.

Six glass columns (7 mm diameter) were run in parallel, each connected to its own pump and effluent container (compare Figure 1). A support layer of glass beads and glass wool was added, and the filter bed was packed by pipetting degassed adsorbent suspension into the column. The experimental setup included a 200 L stainless steel tank, the packed columns, and polyethylene tubing (Festo, Germany). Samples were taken manually with polypropylene syringes or automatically with sampling units. Samples were prepared, filtered and stored as described in section 2.3.1.

Table 1 Design parameters of the CD-RSSCT

Adsorbent	$d_{p,LC}$ (mm)	$d_{p,SC}$ (mm)	EBCT _{LC} (min)	EBCT _{SC} (s)	bed height (cm)	Re	Re*Sc	Flow rate (mL/min)
IX1	0,7	0,115	3	4,86	1,48	0,92	711	7,06
IX2	0,7	0,115	3	4,86	1,48	0,92	711	7,06
AC1	1,386	0,115	16	12,05	1,84	0,53	530	6,41
AC2	1,1	0,115	16	9,57	2,91	0,53	530	6,41
AC3	1,08	0,115	16	9,39	3,02	0,53	530	6,41
SMC1	0,527	0,115	3	8,57	2,02	0,37	500	5,45
SMC2	0,527	0,115	3	8,57	2,02	0,56	563	5,45

Berlin tap water, which was spiked with highly concentrated OMP stock solutions (including 15 PFAS and 8 iPMT), was used as the feed for the RSSCTs. Information on DOC, hardness, and inorganic anion concentrations as well as the OMP influent concentrations in the test water are listed in Table SI 3 and Table SI 4. All RSSCTs were performed in duplicate and operated up to a throughput of approx. 100,000 bed volumes (BV). The individual adsorbents of an adsorbent group (GAC, IX, or SMC) were each tested simultaneously. The experiment was therefore carried out three times with a maximum of 6 columns operating in parallel.

Figure 1 RSSCT flow diagram with six columns in parallel.

2.3.3 RSSCT breakthrough curve fitting and calculation of usage rates

In order to inter- and extrapolate effluent data to determine exact breakthroughs, RSSCT breakthrough curves were fitted to an S-shaped model curve using equation (3) as described by Chu et al. (2020):

$$y(x) = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-k(x-x_0)})} \quad (3)$$

With k and x_0 being model fitting parameters, x being the number of treated BV and $y(x)$ being the normalized effluent concentration c/c_0 at the respective number of BV. The fitting was performed in Python (version 3.11) using the `curve_fit` function from the `scipy.optimize` package. The breakthrough data was then used to determine the BV_{25} , BV_{50} , and BV_{95} value of the investigated PFAS and iPMT during the RSSCT experiment, which corresponds to the number of BV until a normalized effluent concentration of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.95 is reached (which corresponds to 25, 50, and 95% breakthrough). The BV_{25} serves as a conservative estimate for the maximum throughput, as limit values in DW are often very low and adsorbents often cannot be operated to full breakthrough. The BV_{50} value describes the inflection point of the breakthrough curve and allows a direct comparison with isotherm data (as described by Worch (2012)). The BV_{95} value serves as a measure for the complete breakthrough. The usage rate at 50% breakthrough (UR_{50}) in mg adsorbent per L of water treated was calculated by equation (4) as described by Corwin and Summers (2010):

$$UR_{50} = \frac{\rho_{bed}}{BV_{50}} \quad (4)$$

with bed density ρ_{bed} determined as described by Worch (2012).

2.4 Large- and pilot-scale groundwater treatment

2.4.1 Pilot site description

Due to legacy contamination from the former Berlin Tegel airport, three wells operated by BWB were disconnected from DW production. To address the contamination, BWB installed a large-scale GAC plant to treat the highly contaminated groundwater. A pilot plant with IX and SMC was installed at the same site by BWB within the PROMISCES project. A flow diagram of the large-scale remediation GAC plant and pilot plant with IX and SMC is shown in Figure 2 and the corresponding photos in Figure 3.

The PFAS-contaminated GW is first pumped into a feed tank and aerated (with a volume flow of 150 m³/h). The GW is then filtered through two parallel lines (A and B) using sand filters (SF) before being directed to the GAC treatment. In this process, the contaminated GW passes through four GAC filters in series per line (line A: A1-A4, line B: B1-B4), with an EBCT of 16 minutes per filter, resulting in a total EBCT of 64 minutes per line. All filters are operated downstream. Subsequently, the treated GW is infiltrated into the subsurface and, through groundwater recharge, remains part of the water cycle.

The pilot plant consists of three columns: the first column with IX1 (IX1A) receives the effluent of GAC filter B2, the second column with IX1 (IX1B) and the column with SMC1 receive the effluent of the sand filters in line B (SFB). The columns of the pilot plant are operated in upflow mode, each with an EBCT of 3 minutes. While the large-scale GAC plant started operation in November 2022, the pilot plant began its operation in February 2024, with a volume flow of 40 L/h for each column.

Figure 2 Flow diagram of the large-scale GAC plant and pilot-scale SMC and IX plant for groundwater treatment.

Figure 3 Pictures of the large-scale GAC plant during construction in 2021 (left) and installation of the IX- and SMC-pilot (right) in 2024.

2.4.2 Sampling campaign for PFAS CALUX and suspect screening

Samples for suspect screening and PFAS CALUX were taken in February and March 2024 (sampling campaign 1 and 2) at the pilot and large-scale GW treatment plant using 1 L glass bottles. Samples of every influent and effluent of the pilot plant as well as the last GAC filter of the B line (GAC B4, Figure 2) were taken. An overview of all samples taken is given in Table 2. The samples were transported refrigerated to UBA on the same day and further processed there as described in section 2.5.3.

The extracts obtained were analyzed using PFAS CALUX, suspect screening, and PFAS target analysis ('target_eluate'). In addition, the original water samples (without additional enrichment) from all sampling points except B4 were also analyzed using PFAS target analysis ('target').

Table 2 Overview of sampling IDs, times and points for suspect screening and PFAS CALUX.

Sample ID	Sampling date	Description
SFB_1	19/02/24	Effluent of rapid sand filters in line B; influent of IX1B and SMC1
SFB_2	12/03/24	
IX1A_1	19/02/24	Effluent of IX column IX1A
IX1A_2	12/03/24	
IX1B_1	19/02/24	Effluent of IX column IX1B
IX1B_2	12/03/24	
SMC1_1	19/02/24	Effluent of SMC1 column
SMC1_2	12/03/24	
B2_1	19/02/24	Effluent of second GAC filter in line B (B2); influent of IX1A
B2_2	12/03/24	
B4_1	19/02/24	Effluent of last GAC filter in line B (B4)
B4_2	12/03/24	

The biological PFOA-equivalents derived using the PFAS CALUX (BEQ) were compared with PFOA-equivalents derived by converting the PFAS target analysis results with relative potency factors based on PFAS CALUX (CEQ), as described by Behnisch et al. (2021), as well as relative potency factors based on animal data and in-silico modelling (TEQ), as proposed in the amendment of the EU Water Framework Directive COM EU 440 (2022).

2.5 Analytical methods

2.5.1 Target analyses of PFAS, iPMT, and other OMP

All PFAS analyses during the jar test experiment (except for TFMSA analysis) were conducted using a high-performance liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) method described by Ingold et al. (2023). All PFAS samples obtained from RSSCT, pilot- and large-scale adsorbent tests were analyzed by a HPLC-MS/MS method described by Zietzschmann et al. (2023). The other OMP (including TFMSA) were analyzed by a HPLC MS/MS method described by Zeeshan et al. (2023).

2.5.2 Quantification and characterization of DOM

DOC was quantified with a TOC analyzer that uses a catalytic oxidation method (TOC-L, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) in accordance with a standard method (DIN EN 1484). Ultraviolet (UV) absorption at 254 nm (UV₂₅₄) was quantified with a Lambda 12 dual beam spectral photometer (Perkin-Elmer, USA) with 10 mm quartz cuvettes (Suprasil, Hellma, Germany).

The DOM in all samples was characterized using size exclusion chromatography with UV₂₅₄ and online organic carbon detections (LC-OCD-UVD model 8, DOC-Labor Huber, Germany). The method uses advanced oxidation/mineralization. A detailed description is given by Huber et al. (2011). The LC-OCD peaks were allocated as described by Haberkamp et al. (2007) and assigned to different DOM fractions: biopolymers (BP), humic acids (HA), building blocks (BB), low molecular weight acids (LMWA), and neutrals (LMWN).

2.5.3 PFAS CALUX bioassay

The water samples were prepared by UBA with weak anion exchange solid phase extraction in accordance with the corresponding standard operating procedure (enrichment factor 10,000) developed by BDS for further testing by UBA and BDS (bioassays), BWB (target analysis), and BAFG (suspect screening). The extracts were diluted in DMSO for the bioassays and in methanol for the chemical analysis.

The test strategy for toxicity testing of potentially PFAS-contaminated water samples was adapted from Deliverable 1.5 (Behnisch et al. 2021). The total PFAS content of the extracted water samples was determined using the TTR-TR β CALUX by BDS and UBA. The CALUX bioassays are based on genetically modified cell lines, each of which has a receptor-specific response element and a dependent reporter gene for luciferase. When a substance binds to the receptor, luciferase is ultimately formed. Through addition of luciferin, the appropriate substrate for luciferase, light is emitted. The amount of light produced is proportional to the amount of ligand-specific receptor binding, which is benchmarked against the specific reference compounds. The results are expressed as bioanalytical equivalents (BEQs), i.e. the substances in the samples have an effect like the corresponding equivalent concentration of PFOA (as the reference substance in the TTR-TR β CALUX).

The TTR-TR β CALUX bioassay is based on competition between PFAS and the thyroid hormone T4 for binding sites on transthyretin (TTR) transport proteins. In the TTR-binding assay, binding competition between a fixed concentration of T4 and a dilution series of sample extracts is studied. Increasing concentrations of relevant substances capable of competing with T4 for TTR-binding sites will result in a decreased amount of TTR-bound T4. Following separation of TTR-bound and unbound compounds (T4 and relevant substances), the amount of TTR-bound T4 is determined using the TR β CALUX bioassay. An inhibition of binding of T4 to the TTR greater than 80% is considered an effect.

On each 96 well plate, complete calibration curves for each respective bioassay were also analysed using the relevant reference compounds. Ultrapure water was used as negative control.

2.5.4 Suspect screening

Water samples prepared by UBA (cf. compare section 2.5.3) were analysed via liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS) in a database-assisted suspect-screening approach. A detailed description of the method is provided in Deliverable D1.4 (Dietrich et al. 2024).

Samples were sent to BAFG by project partners and were stored in the refrigerator at 5°C until analysis. The methanolic extracts (enrichment factor 10,000, cf. section 2.5.3) were diluted 1:2000 in ultrapure water and spiked with a mix of three surrogate standards used for instrumental quality control at concentration levels of 1000 ng/L for bezafibrate-d4, 500 ng/L for olmesartan-d6, and 2000 ng/L for iopromide-d3. Aqueous samples from the pilot plant were filtered through 0.45 μ m cellulose-acetate-filters prior to shipping. At BAFG facilities, samples were spiked with surrogate standards, analogously to SPE extracts, without further dilution.

For chromatographic separation, LC-MS grade acetonitrile was obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Formic acid (LC-MS grade) was received from Sigma-Aldrich (Seelze, Germany). Ultrapure water was generated with a Milli-Q water purification system (Merck Millipore, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Surrogate standards bezafibrate-d4, olmesartan-d6, and iopromide-d3 were purchased from TRC (North York, Canada). Chromatographic separation was achieved using an Agilent 1260 infinity (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) system equipped with a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (2.1 x 150 mm, 3.5 μ m, 95 Å; Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) coupled to a Phenomenex Security GuardTM AQ C18 column (3 x 4 mm; Phenomenex, Aschaffenburg, Germany).

100 µL of sample were injected into the system. Ultrapure water with 0.1% formic acid (eluent A) and acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid (eluent B) were used as mobile phases at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min and a column temperature of 40°C, with the gradient shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Chromatographic gradient used for suspect screening of PFAS and iPMTs in the BAFG suspect screening method.

Time	Eluent A	Eluent B
0 min	98%	2%
1 min	98%	2%
2 min	80%	20%
16.5 min	0%	100%
22 min	0%	100%
22.1 min	98%	2%
25 min	98%	2%

Mass spectrometric analysis was performed with a TripleToF 6600 hybrid quadrupole time-of-flight spectrometer (Q-ToF-MS/MS; Sciex, Darmstadt, Germany) equipped with an electron spray ionization source, and operated in positive and negative ionization mode in two separate runs. Data acquisition was done by means of full scan experiments ranging from 100 to 1200 Da. Subsequently, MS2 spectra of the eight most intense peaks were recorded via information dependent acquisition (IDA) with a collision energy of 40 V and collision energy spread of 15 V. Acquisition time of full scan and the IDA experiments were 150 ms and 30 ms.

For data processing, data received from the measurements were first transferred to the open data format mzXML using Proteo Wizard 3.0 (proteowizard.sourceforge.io). Peak picking was performed by an algorithm in R as described in Dietrich et al. (2022). Following peak picking, features detected in different samples were aligned based on their similarity in retention time and mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) (m/z -tolerance 20 ppm, retention time tolerance 20 s). Identification of suspects was achieved by matching high resolution mass, MS2 spectra, and retention time of aligned features with a collective spectral library (CSL). The CSL was fed with the respective information from analyses of authentic reference standards, mostly on the same instruments or by cooperating laboratories, and currently consists of about 1,400 substances (January 2025).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Laboratory-scale adsorbent testing

3.1.1 Competitive adsorption of DOM

The DOC and UV₂₅₄ data from the jar test in Figure 4 show that the AC and, in particular, the IX, remove large proportions of the DOM, while the AA show substantially lower removals or even DOC leaching.

Among the AC, highest DOC removals and UV₂₅₄ abatements were seen with charcoal-based AC5, followed by lignite AC6, and very similar results were obtained for the different bituminous AC (AC1-4).

The IX from different manufacturers showed only slight differences in the removals of DOC and abatements of UV₂₅₄ with very low standard deviations (e.g. 2 % for DOC and 3 % for UV₂₅₄ at 50 mg/L). This indicates very similar affinities towards DOM which could be attributed to similar product characteristics. PFAS-specific IX are less affected by DOM competition than conventional IX, removing up to 4-5 times less DOC, depending on IX dose and DOM composition (Dixit et al. 2021a).

SMC4 showed an inhomogeneous pattern: while the highest DOC removal of all AA was found at an adsorbent dose of 50 mg/L (28 %), a two-digit negative removal was quantified at the lower adsorbent dose of 20 mg/L (-34 %).

CDP also showed very negative removals of DOC and UV₂₅₄ at both doses. Previous laboratory scale studies with CDP did not investigate the decline of DOC or UV₂₅₄ (Wang et al. 2020; Ching et al. 2020), whereas a pilot-scale column study with CDP reported TOC removals below 10 % (Hwang et al. 2021). Low DOC and UV₂₅₄ removals by BEA could be attributed to size exclusion of most DOM fractions, as suggested by Fu et al. (2022).

Figure 4 Removals of DOC and abatements of UV₂₅₄ in jar tests with spiked DW after 48 h equilibration time at 20 and 50 mg/L adsorbent dosage (dry weight). Reference sample c₀: 4.5 mg/L DOC, 9.4 m⁻¹ UV₂₅₄ (Rückbeil et al. 2025, *submitted*).

Integration of peak areas within selected detection time ranges of the LC-OCD-UVD chromatograms (Figure 5) showed that the DOM in the test water consists of approximately 45 % HA, 29 % BB, 13 % LMWN, 13 % LMWA, and no BP. Removal by AC was highest for LMWA (on average 65 % at 50 mg/L), followed by the BB (on average 50 % at 50 mg/L). Previous studies revealed that adsorption competition between OMP and DOM on AC is dominated by LMWA and LMWN, especially the UV₂₅₄ active part of LMWA and LMWN, which lower adsorption capacities compared to water with lower DOM content (Zietzschmann et al. 2016; Schumann et al. 2023).

For IX, highest removals were observed for HA (on average 82 % at 50 mg/L) and BB (on average 51 % at 50 mg/L), therefore a high proportion of HA and BB appears to be particularly detrimental to the performance of the IX. These findings are also supported by Hu et al. (2014). Removals of HA, BB, and LMWA by IX is dominated by electrostatic interactions between positively charged quaternary ammonia groups of the IX and deprotonated acid groups of the DOM fractions, whereas the removal of LMWN can be attributed to physical adsorption processes (Cornelissen et al. 2008). It can be concluded that although the IX achieved the highest capacities for many PFAS among the adsorbents tested, especially short-chain compounds, it must be assumed that there is considerable competition from components of the DOM, and that these reduce the capacity of the IX, as discussed further in section 2.3.1.

Figure 5 LC-OCD-UVD chromatograms from jar tests for both adsorbent doses (20 and 50 mg/L) of selected adsorbents in direct comparison with the reference sample c_0 . With biopolymers (BP), humic acids (HA), building blocks (BB), low molecular weight acids (LMWA), and low molecular weight neutrals (LMWN), UV: ultraviolet absorbance at 254 nm, OC: organic carbon (Rückbeil et al. 2025, *submitted*).

The LC-OCD-UVD chromatograms of samples after treatment with BEA, SMC1, SMC3, and SMC5 were so similar to the reference sample that no quantitative calculation of the removal of the individual organic carbon (OC) fractions was performed. The LC-OCD results were hereby consistent with the very low DOC and UV₂₅₄ removals shown in Figure 4. From this it can be concluded that SMC removes PFAS particularly selectively and that competition for adsorption sites by DOM is negligible. Nevertheless, it is still possible that high DOM contents slow down the adsorption kinetics and reduce the capacity via pore blocking and fouling when operating a fixed bed filter.

The LC-OCD-UVD chromatograms of samples after treatment with CDP showed elevated peaks, which overlap with the detection times of HA, BB, LMWA, and LMWN in the OC data series and with the detection times of HA, BB and LMWA in the UV₂₅₄ data series. This is consistent with the high negative DOC removal and UV₂₅₄ abatement of CDP shown in Figure 4.

Elevated DOC concentrations after adsorbent dosage might be related to adsorbent leaching or impurities introduced during transport or storage. Further studies are recommended to investigate the increase of DOC and UV₂₅₄ after addition of SMC2, SMC4, and CDP.

3.1.2 Removal of PFAS, iPMT and other OMP

Jar test results

The removal of all OMP included in the jar test experiment is shown in Figure 6. A clear correlation between perfluorinated carbon chain length and PFAS removal was observed across all adsorbents. Bituminous AC (AC1-AC4) outperformed charcoal-based AC (AC5) and lignite-based AC (AC6), especially for short-chain PFCA and HFPO-DA. Differences among bituminous AC were minimal, suggesting similar AC properties.

The only macroporous IX (IX1) was the most effective at removing short-chain PFCA. All IX removed PFCA with more than six perfluorinated carbon atoms completely at both doses, making it difficult to assess performance differences. IX were generally more efficient for long-chain PFCA than the tested AC and AA adsorbents. IX also excelled at removing HFPO-DA, with only slight differences between products (5% standard deviation at 50 mg/L).

The two bentonite-based products (SMC1 and SMC2) showed similar or better PFAS removal than AC. In contrast, the three palygorskite-based SMC products (SMC3, SMC4, and SMC5) were ineffective, with SMC3 and SMC5 showing no removal of short-chain PFAS, though some long-chain PFAS removal was observed. SMC4 achieved 20% removal of short-chain PFAS, such as PFPeA, at 50 mg/L.

BEA and CDP showed poor PFBA removal, and only low removals for short-chain PFCA like PFPeA and PFHxA (<8% at 50 mg/L for BEA). CDP performed similarly to AC for these substances, but neither adsorbent removed HFPO-DA as effectively as AC or IX.

Previous studies have shown that bituminous AC can achieve higher PFAS loadings than other AC types, likely due to its favorable pore distribution for PFAS molecular sizes (Cantoni et al. 2021). Hydrophobic interactions and electrostatic forces are the primary mechanisms for PFAS removal by AC (Grieco et al. 2021; Gagliano et al. 2020).

Unlike AC and most AA, all IX were effective at removing TFMSA, with macroporous IX1 showing particular efficiency. Other PFSA were 100% removed by all IX at 20 mg/L. IX1 differs from other IX primarily in its macroporous structure, which may provide easier access for PFAS to active sites

compared to the gelular IX. Other studies support this influence of IX structure (Boyer et al. 2021; Dixit et al. 2021b).

Gellular IX products from different manufacturers showed similar performance for all OMP, suggesting that manufacturer choice is less important. All PFAS-specific IX adsorbents rely on electrostatic interactions between PFAS and quaternary ammonia groups, as well as hydrophobic interactions with the PFAS alkyl chain and, for long-chain PFAS, the IX polystyrene backbone. These mechanisms explain the better retention of long-chain PFAS and the difficulty of regenerating PFAS-specific resins via conventional brine regeneration (Dixit et al., 2019).

Surface modification with cationic surfactants, like aliphatic amines, enhances the hydrophobicity and anion exchange capacity of SMC (Jiang et al. 2023; Mukhopadhyay et al. 2021). The removal of anionic PFAS is then primarily driven by hydrophobic interactions, though electrostatic interactions and ligand exchange can also play a role (Jiang et al. 2023; Mukhopadhyay et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2024).

Despite being grouped as SMC, SMC1, SMC2, SMC3, and SMC5 show significant differences in PFAS removal effectiveness. These variations might stem from differences in the clay mineral properties (e.g., fibrous vs. layered) or the surface functionalization. Manufacturers provided no details on the functionalization process.

Literature suggests that PFSA are more easily removed than PFCA with similar perfluorinated C-chain lengths (Plumlee et al. 2022; Cantoni et al. 2021; Dixit et al. 2019; Jiang et al. 2023; Ching et al. 2020). This may be due to the stronger acidity of sulfonic acids, which enhances interactions with amines. Additionally, the presence of an ether group (as in HFPO-DA) reduces removability compared to PFOA, likely because it interferes with hydrophobic interactions.

This study confirms several findings from a large US pilot column study on PFAS removal from GW with varying DOC levels (0.3 to 2.3 mg/L, pH 7.3 – 8.3): 1) bituminous AC outperforms AC from other raw materials; 2) IX and SMC1 achieve higher PFAS loadings than AC; 3) gellular IX from different manufacturers perform similarly; and 4) CDP is less effective at removing PFAS than AC, IX, or SMC (Plumlee et al. 2022; Pannu et al. 2023; Hwang et al. 2021). Hwang et al. (2021) found a negative correlation between days until PFAS breakthrough and DOC concentration for AC, while SMC1 and CDP performed similarly across DOC levels. The DOC impact on AC is significant, as shown by isotherm studies in DOC-free water (Olshansky et al. 2022). Olshansky et al. (2022) conducted isotherm studies with AC2 in deionized water, finding K_d values up to 2000 times higher than in this study.

Most other OMP were primarily removed by AC, especially those with aromatic rings such as BDMA, BETMAC, BTA, and CBM. Polar compounds like CG and MPSA were poorly removed by AC. IX removed BTA, but less effectively than AC.

BDMA and BETMAC were completely removed by BEA and SMC4 (100% at 50 mg/L), while the other adsorbents had no effect. SMC4 was particularly effective for BTA removal (100% at 20 mg/L). CDP was the only adsorbent that removed CG (71% at 50 mg/L). DIOTOG was removed by SMC4 and BEA (100%), while MPSA was not removed by any adsorbent. IX effectively removed anionic pharmaceuticals and sweeteners (DCF, SMX, VSA, ACE, SAC), but not neutral or positively charged compounds.

Figure 6 Removals of OMP in test water from jar tests at adsorbent dosages of 20 and 50 mg/L (dry weight) after 48 h equilibration time. Reference concentrations are listed in Table SI 2 (Rückbeil et al. 2025, *submitted*).

RSSCT results

An overview of all BV_{25} , BV_{50} , and BV_{95} values derived during the RSSCT experiment is given in Figure 7. The breakthrough curves with fitted model curves for six adsorbents for one PFAS (TFMSA) and one iPMT (DMBSA) are also shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 as examples for data evaluation. All data sets in which a breakthrough could be quantified (normalized effluent concentration > 0.05) were accurately described by the applied S-curve model (coefficient of determination R^2 always > 0.59, mean $R^2 = 0.91$).

The results of the RSSCT confirm important findings of the jar tests: short-chain PFAS are generally more difficult to remove than long-chain PFAS, and sulfonic acids are better removed than carboxylic acids. AC cannot be used to achieve economic runtimes for short-chain PFAS removal such as PFBA and TFMSA, as these substances achieved 95 % breakthrough with all three AC after just a few thousand BV. The highest throughputs until breakthrough of PFBA and TFMSA were achieved with IX1, but other IX or SMC may also be viable alternatives to AC to remove these short-chain compounds. While for all PFSA with at least two perfluorinated C atoms no breakthrough within the first 100,000 BV for all IX and SMC tested was seen, SMC1 and SMC2 proved to be the best adsorbents for removing long-chain PFCA.

Emerging PFAS, such as the tested PFECA, HFPO-DA, and ADONA, and the polyfluorinated substance H4-PFOS, are more difficult to remove than the now banned substances PFOA and PFOS they substitute. This illustrates that a ban on a single perfluorinated substance is insufficient as long as it is simply replaced by a very similar but not banned substance. On the contrary, the substitutes bring additional uncertainties, as no information is available on their removal, and analytical methods must first be developed to be able to quantify them in environmental samples (Evich et al. 2022; Hale et al. 2020a, 2020b).

The UR_{50} derived with the RSSCT are visualized in Figure 10, where a dashed horizontal line indicates a UR_{50} of 25 mg/L to identify strongly adsorbing compounds, as proposed by Kempisty et al. (2022). This limit for a feasible UR_{50} should not be taken as an absolute value to define feasibility of GAC treatment, but as a practice-oriented size range derived from discussions among water professionals to avoid excessive GAC change out during filter operation (Kempisty et al., 2020). Based on the respective bed densities of the RSSCT, a UR of 25 mg/L refers to 9,000-11,000 bed volumes of IX treatment, 13,000-15,000 BV of GAC treatment, and 13,000-20,000 BV of SMC treatment.

It can be seen that feasible UR_{50} can be achieved for PFSA with 5 or more perfluorinated C-atoms as well as PFCA with 6 or more perfluorinated C-atoms. The IX and SMC that were tested were able to achieve significantly lower UR for all PFAS. For the iPMT and other OMP, a large part of the UR_{50} could only be determined for the GAC, as the removals by IX and SMC were too small, which once again emphasizes the broader removal effect of the GAC.

ATA, AAMPS, and DTA are examples of OMP for which no feasible UR could be achieved with any adsorbent under the experimental conditions described. These substances should be classified as particularly critical for adsorptive water treatment.

In Figure 10, the UR_{50} classification for GAC has been used for all adsorbents, which enables direct comparability with reference to the same adsorbent mass. However, it could just as well make sense to adjust the limit for a feasible UR_{50} depending on the adsorbent price. This means that if, for example, the price of an IX is 5 times higher, then a feasible UR_{50} for the IX would have to be 5 times lower than that of the GAC in order to be competitive. However, as the prices for adsorbents fluctuate and are subject to uncertainty, this evaluation has been omitted here. Specific adsorbent costs are discussed in more detail in section 3.2.1.

In summary, IX and SMC in particular remove PFAS much more selectively than AC. The macroporous IX1 proved to be the best adsorbent for short-chain PFAS, while SMC1 was the best adsorbent for long-chain PFAS. However, as already indicated in the jar test, AC was the only adsorbent group investigated that also achieved a broader removal of other OMP, such as MEL or DPG. The choice of the best adsorptive treatment option is therefore strongly dependent on the composition of the OMP and the treatment objective, and should be decided individually according to site specific conditions.

While AC and in particular IX also showed high removals of DOM, no competition for adsorption sites by DOM could be determined for the SMC.

Based on the laboratory results presented, IX1 and SMC1 were selected for subsequent piloting, with IX1 showing highest removal for short-chain PFAS and SMC being especially PFAS-selective.

Figure 7 OMP breakthroughs during RSSCT experiments with test water quantified by BV₂₅, BV₅₀, and BV₉₅. OMP reference concentrations in the influent are listed in Table SI 4. BV₂₅, BV₅₀, or BV₉₅ values that were determined via extrapolation beyond the experimental data (> 100,000 BV) are displayed as > 100,000 BV. 'no removal' indicates a normalized effluent concentration > 0.25 within the first 500 BV treated.

Figure 8 Normalized effluent concentration of Trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (TFMSA) with AC1, AC2, IX1, IX2, SMC1 and SMC2 during RSSCT experiments (duplicate A and B) with test water. Interpolated BV₂₅, BV₅₀ and BV₉₅ values are indicated by dashed lines. Coefficient of determination (R²) indicates respective model fit.

Figure 9 Normalized effluent concentration of 2,4-dimethylbenzene-1-sulfonic acid (DMBSA) with AC1, AC2, IX1, IX2, SMC1 and SMC2 during RSSCT experiments (duplicate A and B) with test water. Interpolated BV_{25} , BV_{50} and BV_{95} values are indicated by dashed lines. Coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates respective model fit.

Figure 10 Usage rates based on number of bed volumes until 50 % breakthrough (UR₅₀) derived with RSSCT data. If no breakthrough occurred (normalized effluent concentration < 0.05), no UR₅₀ was calculated (marked by a green point). If the OMP was not removable by the adsorbent (normalized effluent concentration > 0.25 within the first 500 BV treated), no usage rate was calculated either (marked by a red x). A dashed horizontal line indicates a UR₅₀ of 25 mg/L, a limit for feasibility of GAC treatment as proposed by Kempisty et al. (2022).

3.2 Large and pilot-scale groundwater treatment

3.2.1 PFAS removal, cost analysis, and UV₂₅₄ correlation

The breakthrough curves for the pilot plant and the first adsorber of the large-scale GAC plant (B1) for the sum parameters PFAS-4 (20 ng/L) and PFAS-20 (100 ng/L), as well as selected short- and long-chain PFCA and PFSA are shown in Figure 11. It can be seen that the sum parameter PFAS-4 is more critical than PFAS-20 as breakthrough occurs first in all adsorbers and would therefore determine the runtime.

While in the first GAC adsorber the PFAS-20 limit value is already exceeded after 4,500 BV and the PFAS-4 limit value after 3,000 BV, the IX can treat 35,000 and 15,000 BV before the PFAS-20 or PFAS-4 limit value is exceeded. The SMC can even treat 30,000 BV until the PFAS-4 limit value is reached. In case of SMC, the PFAS-20 limit value was not exceeded during the measurement period, and linear extrapolation was used to estimate that the PFAS-20 limit value may be reached at around 140,000 BV.

At the pilot-site, the PFAS-4 limit value would therefore be the limiting factor, as breakthrough occurs first for all adsorbents. This is mainly due to the PFAS composition at the site, which predominantly consists of substances included in the PFAS-4 sum parameter (PFOS, PFHxS, PFHxA, see Table SI 5).

In the GAC-IX treatment train (IX1A) it can be observed that the GAC pretreatment significantly delays breakthrough of long-chain PFAS like PFOS and the sum parameters PFAS-4 and PFAS-20 (to which PFOS contributes mostly at the pilot site). The PFAS-4 breakthrough in the IX1A column at 70,000 BV, whereas the PFAS-20 breakthrough appears at 99,500 BV.

In contrast, short-chain PFBA is poorly adsorbed on GAC, therefore the PFBA breakthrough in the IX1A column is similar to that of the IX1B column. However, PFBA desorption was observed after GAC replacement, where the effluent concentration exceeded the influent concentration. This effect should be considered when short-chain PFAS are present, and would not favor a GAC-IX treatment train when a larger proportion of short-chain compounds or very low treatment target values are present. The GAC-IX treatment train is particularly recommended if a broad removal of OMP is to be achieved and short-chain PFAS are also present. However, desorption effects are to be expected if the GAC is changed prematurely and the IX column continues to operate. Furthermore, competition for adsorption sites is to be expected if DOM is present, which limits the capacity of the GAC and the IX.

Overall, the pilot column with SMC achieved the highest number of treated BV up to complete breakthrough for both PFAS sum parameters. This may be due to the high selectivity of the SMC, which makes it insensitive to the high DOC content at the site, as shown in the laboratory tests (compare section 3.1.2). GAC-SMC could be a particularly effective treatment train if broad OMP removal is to be achieved and high DOM concentrations are present. In this case, most of the OMP can be removed by GAC, while the PFAS can be removed particularly selectively by the SMC with minor adsorption site competition on the SMC by DOM.

The German drinking water limit values used for comparison do not apply to the treatment of GW at the legacy contaminated site, where the inflow concentrations significantly exceed those expected in DW (max. one to two digit ng/L range per single compound according to Ingold et al. (2023)). The data collected therefore cannot be used to draw direct conclusions about actual runtimes for the treatment of DW with significantly lower influent concentrations. However, the results allow

comparison of the adsorbents with regard to their ability to remove the target substances in a water matrix comparable to DW.

Figure 11 PFAS influent and effluent data of the IX and SMC pilot and first GAC adsorber (B1) of large-scale GW treatment plant. German PFAS-4 and PFAS-20 DW limit values (20 ng/L and 100 ng/L) are indicated by dashed horizontal line. Interrupted operation due to GAC exchange and maintenance indicated by orange vertical lines.

The normalized effluent UV_{254} absorbance is compared with the normalized effluent concentration of PFAS-20, PFBA, and PFOS in Figure 12. Previous studies have already shown that for iPMT and other OMP, correlations with the removal of UV_{254} can be observed during removal by AC (Schumann et al. 2023; Jekel and Zietzschmann 2018; Altmann et al. 2016). The data from the pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant were used to make similar estimates for the removal of PFAS by GAC, IX, and SMC. With the exception of two outliers, a good correlation was observed with GAC between normalized UV_{254} absorbance, PFOS concentration, and PFAS-20, but not for the poorly removable PFBA compound. With the IX, a correlation between normalized PFBA concentration and normalized UV_{254} absorbance was also evident. With the SMC, no correlation could be observed due to the very low DOM removal.

In practical application, the site- and water quality-specific correlation between target PFAS and UV_{254} removal needs to be established first. Afterwards, UV_{254} real time monitoring can provide a fast and cost-effective monitoring method to estimate PFAS breakthrough in GAC and IX treatment. However, it cannot be recommended as an option for monitoring PFAS breakthrough in SMC adsorbers.

Figure 12 Comparison of normalized effluent UV_{254} absorbance and normalized effluent concentration of PFBA, PFOS, and PFAS-20.

Very different data on the adsorbent costs of GAC, IX, and SMC were found in literature (Riegel et al. 2023; Barr Engineering Co. and Hazen and Sawyer 2023). The numbers given in Table 4 therefore only represent an initial range and should only be used with a safety margin in further estimates.

Additionally, it should be noted that other operation and maintenance costs like reactivation (GAC) or disposal or incineration (IX, SMC), as well as investment costs, are not considered. Assuming IX is 2-6 times more expensive per m^3 than GAC, it would need to treat a correspondingly higher number of BV in order to be more economical than GAC.

This would be the case for PFAS-4 and PFAS-20 at the investigated pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant. But SMC may be more cost effective for use on site. However, the high selectivity of the SMC also means that other iPMT or pharmaceuticals are hardly or not at all removed, as our laboratory tests have shown. The use of SMC is therefore limited to waters in which PFAS are the primary compound to be removed.

Table 4 Specific adsorbent media costs.

Adsorbent	Specific adsorbent media costs (€/m ³)	References
GAC	2,000-4,300	Riegel et al. (2023); Barr Engineering Co. and Hazen and Sawyer (2023)
IX	8,000-13,500	Riegel et al. (2023); Barr Engineering Co. and Hazen and Sawyer (2023)
SMC	5,500-7,600	Barr Engineering Co. and Hazen and Sawyer (2023)

For a broader removal of iPMT and other OMP from DOC-rich source water, processes with GAC or a combination of GAC and IX are particularly powerful, as our data show. However, due to the high specific adsorbent costs of IX, a precise cost analysis needs be carried out based on site-specific conditions (like treatment target, DOM composition) and the costs and benefits compared. No general recommendation can be made for this treatment train. A potentially more cost-effective combination of GAC and SMC could also be interesting for subsequent studies. However, when applied in the DW sector, national regulations must also be considered in regards to which adsorbents are actually permitted. In Germany, for example, this would currently only be GAC, as defined by the annex of the German drinking water ordinance (TrinkwV 2023).

Modeling tools such as the Planning & design tool for drinking water treatment for PFAS & industrial chemicals developed in PROMISCES can be a cost-effective and fast way to avoid more expensive and lengthy piloting of additional treatment trains (Rückbeil et al., 2024). The disadvantage of modeling solutions is always the high level of uncertainty and the lack of validation with real data. For this reason, it makes sense to combine piloting with modelling as recommended by Burkhardt et al. (2022). The model can be calibrated and validated with existing data and then used to predict new scenarios. In this way, both methods can complement each other and form a flexible and validated decision-making tool (Burkhardt et al. 2022).

3.2.2 PFAS CALUX bioassay results

In Table 5, the TTR-TRβ CALUX (i.e. PFAS CALUX) results for the received groundwater sample extracts are summarised. For all samples, the PFAS CALUX results are expressed as the concentration of reference compound equivalents (µg PFOA-equivalents) per liter of water samples. Typical graphical representation of concentration-response curves in the TTR-TRβ CALUX bioassay from GW samples (analysed by BDS) are shown in Figure 13.

In general, the results in Table 5 show good agreement between the independent testing done at UBA and BDS. The majority of the samples showed no effects above the LOQ. There are deviations in four samples, with samples B4_1 and SMC1_1 being only marginally above the LOQ at BDS. SFB_1 (2.5 µg PFOA eq/L) and SFB_2 (2.7 µg PFOA eq/L) show increased activity in the PFAS CALUX in BDS.

In the SFB_2 sample, UBA found no effects, while for the SFB_1 sample, a concentration dependent effect was seen. This effect did not fall below the 80 % threshold of inhibition, so no activity could be calculated. However, the use of higher concentrations was not possible at UBA because of the cytotoxic effects of DMSO. The results in the bioassays match the processing stages well. Effects after the first treatment step of sand filtration were to be expected. The following additional treatment steps reduce the effects, i.e. the substances contained, below the LOQ. In principle, the results also fit well with the results of chemical analysis (see Figure 15).

The slight deviations in results obtained by UBA and BDS (Table 5) affect the following water samples: BDS recorded four samples above the LOQ (0.99). B4_1 and SMC_1 indicated activities of 1.0 µg PFOA-eq/L, which is marginally above the LOQ. The two SFB samples were slightly higher at 2.5 and 2.7. In the SFB_2 sample, UBA found no effects, while for the SFB_1 sample, a concentration-dependent effect was seen. This effect did not fall below the 80 % threshold of inhibition, so no activity could be calculated. However, the use of higher concentrations was not possible at UBA because of the cytotoxic effects of DMSO.

Figure 13 Typical PFAS CALUX concentration-response curves of selected water-extracts analysed by BDS. Inhibition of the binding of T4 to the TTR protein is expressed as induction relative to the maximum induction of the PFOA reference series (relative induction RI%). “Reinstwasser”: ultrapure water

A comparison of target PFOA equivalents based on different conversion methods is shown in Figure 14. It can be observed that the BEQ values obtained by BDS (based on PFAS CALUX) are above the CEQ and TEQ (calculated by BWB) for samples SFB_1, SMC1_1 and B4_1 (sampling campaign 1) as well as SFB_2 (sampling campaign 2). This could indicate the presence of unknown PFAS compounds in the inflow of the pilot- and large-scale plant or measurement uncertainties. The BEQ values of UBA align with all CEQ and TEQ values, indicating PFOA equivalents below 0.99 µg/L. As expected, the PFOA equivalents are reduced by adsorptive treatment. Both SFB samples (which represent the first effluent after the sand filters) show the highest PFOA equivalents. The samples SMC1_1 and B4_1 showed elevated PFOA equivalents in the PFAS CALUX test method. A comparison with the target analysis results of these samples (original sample and extracts in Figure 14) shows that there is an increased PFPeA and PFHxA concentration in the extracts which was not found in the original sample. This could indicate impurities during concentration or sample storage.

Table 5 PFAS CALUX results of GW sample extracts. * UBA tested PFOA and ultrapure water only in one concentration as an internal control, therefore no activity could be calculated.

Sample	TTR-TR β CALUX (UBA)		TTR-TR β CALUX (BDS)	
	Activity	LOQ	Activity	LOQ
	(μ g PFOA-equivalents/L sample)		(μ g PFOA-equivalents/L sample)	
B4_1	<LOQ	0.99	1.0	0.99
SFB_1	<LOQ	0.99	2.5	0.99
IX1_1	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
IX2_1	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
SMC_1	<LOQ	0.99	1.0	0.99
B2_1	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
B4_2	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
SFB_2	<LOQ	0.99	2.7	0.99
IX1_2	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
IX2_2	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
SMC_2	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
B2_2	<LOQ	0.99	<LOQ	0.99
PFOA 1	-*	-	1.1	0.99
PFOA 2	-*	-	1.9	0.99
PFOA 3	-*	-	1.3	0.99
PFOA 4	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
PFOA 5	-*	-	1.8	0.99
PFOA 6	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 1	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 2	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 3	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 4	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 5	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99
Ultrapure water 6	-*	-	<LOQ	0.99

Figure 14 Comparison of PFAS target analysis (original sample ('target') and rediluted extracts ('target_eluate')) for selected pilot plant and large-scale GW treatment plant samples from the sampling campaign for PFAS CALUX and suspect screening.

Figure 15 PFOA-equivalents in the extracts for both sampling campaigns (1 and 2) at the large-scale GW treatment plant and the pilot plant. PFOA-equivalent calculation based on PFAS CALUX (BEQ, LOQ = 0.99 µg/L) or conversion of PFAS target analysis using relative potency factors based on PFAS CALUX (CEQ, LOQ = 0.003 µg/L) or animal data (TEQ, LOQ = 0.003 µg/L). Values below LOQ are displayed as 0 PFOA equivalents.

3.2.3 Suspect screening

Database assisted suspect screening of samples from the pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant resulted in the identification of four perfluorinated compounds, four industrial chemicals, ten pharmaceuticals and metabolites thereof, and six substances mainly used in personal care products and/or as household chemicals. The latter case is not easily distinguishable from the group of industrial chemicals, as the same products might as well be used in industrial applications, such as laundries. An overview of the detected substances is provided in Figure 16. It should be noted that the applied screening technique does not provide absolute concentrations. Therefore, cumulative intensities provided in Figure 16 must not be interpreted as a sum of concentrations. Different compounds of the same concentrations might appear at different intensities. However, intensity trends within a single compound may provide insight into its actual concentration trend.

During GW treatment plant operation, intensities of three of the four PFAS detected in the effluent of the rapid sand filters (SFB_1 and SFB_2) and effluent of the second GAC filter (B2_1 and B2_2) (i.e. PFPrS, PFHxS, and PFHpS) are reduced and could not be detected after SMC and IX treatment (pilot plant) (Figure 17). Surprisingly, the intensity of the PFHxA was found to be significantly increased in one sample after SMC treatment (SMC1_1). This finding was supported by target analysis showing elevated PFHxA concentrations in the same extract sample. However, since target analysis did not detect PFHxA above 1 ng/L in the original sample, it may be an impurity introduced during sample storage or preparation (compare PFAS target analysis results for extract and original sample in Figure 14). The lowest number of detected substances was found after treatment with four GAC filters in series in the large-scale GW treatment plant (sample B4_1 and B4_2), or after a combination of GAC and IX (sample IX1A_1 and IX1A_2) in the pilot setup. This is supported by findings from the laboratory scale adsorbent screening (compare section 3.1.2), revealing that broad removal of iPMT

is best achieved with AC (or treatment trains combined with AC). The SMC samples showed intensities of dimethyl-ditetradecylammonium that did not appear in other samples.

Figure 16 Cumulated intensity of substances (stacked columns, left y-axis) detected in samples from the pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant analysed via database-assisted suspect screening and number of detected substances (black points, right y-axis). Samples were extracted with methanol (1:10,000) and rediluted in ultrapure water (1:2000). Intensities must not be interpreted as concentrations: different compounds of the same concentration might appear at different intensities. Color code: yellow: industrial chemicals, red: PFAS compounds, pink: pharmaceuticals, blue: household and personal care. Grey arrows: flow path of the large-scale GAC plant and pilot-scale SMC and IX plant.

Figure 17 PFAS compounds detected in samples from the pilot- and large-scale GW treatment plant analysed via database-assisted suspect screening. Samples were extracted with methanol (1:10,000) and rediluted in ultrapure water (1:2000). Intensities must not be interpreted as concentrations; different compounds of the same concentration might appear at different intensities. Grey arrows: flow path of the large-scale GAC plant and pilot-scale SMC and IX plant.

4 Conclusion

To improve knowledge on the removal of PFAS, iPMT, and other OMP from waters with high DOM concentrations (4-5 mg/L DOC), the performance of IX and high-performance adsorbent media specifically tailored to remove PFAS was tested and compared to AC. A broad screening of available tailored adsorbent products included six AC, five SMC, one CDP, and one BEA zeolite. Laboratory-scale equilibrium jar tests showed that PFAS-specific IX and SMC can be relevant alternatives to GAC for PFAS removal.

Dynamic breakthrough behavior of PFAS was studied in RSSCTs, which confirmed jar test results. It was shown that GAC remains the benchmark adsorbent for removing a wide range of iPMT, although it exhibits limited performance in the removal of short-chain PFAS. Strong-base IX were identified as highly effective for PFAS removal, yet their efficiency was significantly compromised by the presence of competing DOM. Bentonite based SMC demonstrated promising potential for PFAS removal, particularly through enhanced selectivity for longer-chain PFAS and compounds with sulfonate groups, and offers a viable option for targeting specific PFAS compounds in complex water matrices.

Pilot-scale column testing of IX and SMC confirmed the laboratory findings and enabled direct comparison with GAC performance in a large-scale plant operated in parallel. These results indicate that treatment trains combining GAC with IX or SMC may offer a more efficient solution for PFAS and iPMT removal in the presence of DOM. However, the choice of the most efficient treatment train is highly dependent on the composition of the PFAS and iPMT, the water matrix, the treatment objective, and economic considerations (e.g. adsorbent media costs).

Bioassays with the PFAS CALUX test (TTR-TR β CALUX) showed no effects above the LOQ in the majority of samples, particularly after adsorption treatment. Database-assisted suspect screening of samples from the pilot-scale IX/SMC and large-scale GAC columns confirmed PFAS removal performance determined via target analysis. The integration of PFAS CALUX tests and suspect target analysis allowed for a more comprehensive assessment of the adsorptive processes, highlighting the importance of detecting unforeseen contaminants and evaluating the effectiveness of adsorbents beyond targeted PFAS.

Overall, this study advances the understanding of competitive adsorption and ion exchange of PFAS and iPMT, and provides valuable insights into the potential of alternative adsorbents.

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Annex

Table SI 1 Information on jar test water (DOM, anions, hardness).

pH	UV ₂₅₄	DOC	SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	o-PO ₄ ³⁻	Fl ⁻	KS _{4.3}	KB _{8.2}	hardne ss (CO ₃ ²⁻)	hardness (Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺)
	1/m	in mg/ L	in mg/L	in mg/ L	in mg/L	in µg/L	in mg/ L	in mmol/L	in mmol/L	in °dH	in °dH
7.5	9.8	4.4	89.0	56. 0	2.7	18.0	0.2	4.02	0.25	11.1	16.4

Table SI 2 OMP reference concentrations in the test water of the jar test experiment.

Parameter	C ₀	unit
UV ₂₅₄	9.4	1/m
DOC	4.5	mg/L
PFBA	9870.0	ng/L
PFPeA	9599.2	ng/L
PFBS	873.3	ng/L
PFHxA	7022.5	ng/L
GenX	7768.3	ng/L
PFHpA	686.7	ng/L
PFHxS	1062.5	ng/L
PFOA	891.7	ng/L
PFNA	936.7	ng/L
PFOS	528.3	ng/L
PFDA	285.8	ng/L
CG	883.1	ng/L
BTA	968.5	ng/L

Parameter	C ₀	unit
BDMA	1535.8	ng/L
BETMAC	1779.2	ng/L
ATA	1350.8	ng/L
PRI	1440.0	ng/L
DIOTOG	1233.3	ng/L
DTA	1073.4	ng/L
VSA	1337.5	ng/L
CBM	1386.7	ng/L
DCF	1377.5	ng/L
SMX	1142.9	ng/L
MPSA	1008.3	ng/L
TFMSA	748.7	ng/L
ACE	1577.5	ng/L
SAC	1035.3	ng/L
AAMPS	1031.8	ng/L

Table SI 3 Information on RSSCT test water (DOM, anions, hardness).

pH	UV ₂₅₄	DOC	SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	o-PO ₄ ³⁻	Fl ⁻	KS _{4.3}	KB _{8.2}	hardne ss (CO ₃ ²⁻)	hardness (Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺)
	1/m	in mg/ L	in mg/L	in mg/ L	in mg/L	in µg/L	in mg/ L	in mmol/L	in mmol/L	in °dH	in °dH
7.5	10.0	4.5	99.0	54. 0	2.6	17.0	0.2	4.3	0.22	11.0	16.3

Table SI 4 OMP influent concentrations (c_0) of the test water during RSSCT experiments in ng/L.

	AC	IX	SMC
AAMPS	1098	1050	1063
ACE	1562	1480	1457
ADONA	1308	1312	1427
ATA	1280	1355	1307
BDMA	2517	2660	4457
BETMAC	5098	3455	3695
CBM	1305	1318	1393
DCF	1407	1293	1447
DIOTOG	1267	1400	1350
DMBSA	2258	2405	2722
DPG	717	945	1132
DTA	854	960	873
H4-PFOS	663	720	444
HFPO-DA	982	989	840
MEL	930	895	1130
MPSA	998	929	975
PFBA	1781	2000	1523
PFBS	1252	1258	1113
PFDA	405	587	934
PFHpA	1203	1160	975
PFHxA	1297	1200	1028
PFHxS	1587	1141	1222
PFNA	882	734	1120
PFOA	1288	917	1309
PFOS	626	606	1046
PFPeA	1275	1320	1091
PFPeS	1303	1059	1159
PRI	1250	1352	1323
SAC	1016	899	1011
SMX	1305	1283	1307
TFMSA	780	947	772
VSA	1265	1215	1282

Table SI 5 Mean influent concentrations (PFAS, inorganic anions, dissolved organic carbon) during full-scale GAC operation (prior to first GAC exchange) and SMC and IX pilot operation. Only PFAS above LOQ shown.

*included in sum parameter PFAS-20, °included in sum parameter PFAS-4.

parameter	GAC7 (B1)	IX1A, SMC1	IX1B	unit
PFAS-20	582.1	556.5	136.1	ng/L
PFAS-4	503.9	468.3	94.8	ng/L
PFBA	4.8*	6.4*	6.5*	ng/L
PFBS	12.8*	19.0*	9.0*	ng/L
PFHpA	4.1*	4.2*	2.2*	ng/L
PFHpS	12.4*	10.5*	1.2*	ng/L
PFHxA	24.6*°	28.4*°	20.2*°	ng/L
PFHxS	202.4*°	207.0*°	45.0*°	ng/L
PFOA	19.9*	19.7*	6.7*	ng/L
PFOS	280.8*°	232.2*°	29.0*°	ng/L
PFPeA	6.8*	7.9*	7.2*	ng/L
PFPeS	15.2*	17.6*	5.1*	ng/L
Cl ⁻		46.0	46.0	mg/L
Fl ⁻		0.2	0.2	mg/L
HCO ₃ ⁻		251.3	251.1	mg/L
NO ₃ ⁻		1.5	1.5	mg/L
SO ₄ ²⁻		114.4	115.5	mg/L
PO ₄ ³⁻		23.0	22.6	µg/L
DOC	4.3	4.3	3.7	mg/L
UV ₂₅₄	8.2	9.1	7.0	1/m